

AI procurement/acquisitions guidance questions for libraries

This document is meant to support libraries when considering purchasing AI software, tools and technologies more widely. Though this was initially written with a library collections environment in mind, it can be applied more broadly. It aims to help you think through potential issues and questions you may wish to ask a vendor.

Much of this applies specifically to [generative AI](#) models as these are popular at the moment.

Many of these questions will focus on data: this is because AI is effectively a very powerful statistical modelling tool. The data used will directly affect the results or outcomes it provides.

Currently, this list is somewhat long. A shortened version with 'core' questions will be written in the near future.

General questions / Internal questions

- Are you sure that (generative) AI is the best tool for this task?
- Do you have a clear problem statement ([or problem specification](#))? E.g. What is the exact problem, desired outcome, and data needed to address the problem?
- Do you hold the appropriate data in the correct format and state and has that data been audited?
 - Is your data suitable, compatible and consistent? Not all programs will be as strict about the state of your data, but it is good practice to have it as well prepared as is feasible in your local setting.
 - If you have answered / commented 'we need more data' - do you need more data overall or do you need more *quality* data?

Technical specifications

The section under this will address some of the more technical aspects of a software. Sellers may not be immediately able to answer these if they are not experts themselves, nevertheless, it would be worth getting insight into these.

Note: Not many softwares use [model](#) and [data](#) sheets/cards yet in the library world, but they are considered best practice in other fields. (They were first introduced by [Google](#).)

Model specifications

- Does this product come with a model sheet or model card?
- What 'type' of AI does this software use? Generative or non-generative?
 - If it is generative AI, who provides the underlying software? (E.g. [OpenAI](#), [Anthropic](#) etc.) Why was this provider used - different companies develop in different ways with different priorities.
- If the engine is from a provider external to your vendor, how will this affect support, troubleshooting, data governance and downtime?
- Are the model's or software's limitations transparent?
- Are you given information on (recommended) use cases and use cases to avoid?
- How much are you able to modify its settings?
- Generally, how transparent is this software? (A lack of transparency can cause vendor lock-in if you would wish to replace / change the software, as you may not be able to understand what is happening within your workflow.)
- Is it necessary to have a product that is integrated into the library management system?
 - Integrated software might be convenient, but may be less flexible and more likely to be 'locked'. It will also come with additional concerns around the data used as there is less control by the institutions well.
- Is this a ['human in the loop'](#) software or will it be fully automated?

Data specifications

- Does the data used to train and test this model have a data card?
 - What data has this model been trained or tested on?
 - Has the data been vetted?
 - Are there indications available around data quality?
 - Has it used open data?
 - What is the copyright status and/or licence of this data?
 - If the software uses a third party model (e.g. a vendor product that runs on Claude/ChatGPT), how can the vendor guarantee the copyright status of the training data?
 - When will it be trained again?
 - Will the software update itself after encountering new data?
 - If the model is or will be trained on your own data, will you remain in control of this data?
 - If the underlying engine is a third-party proprietary large language model (ChatGPT, Claude etc.), how will this be guaranteed?
 - What data will the model have access to?
 - What will the vendor have access to?
 - Will your data be used to further develop other commercial products?

- What is the value of this data?
 - Do you retain the rights to your data?
- How does your data need to be formatted?
 - Is that compatible with how your organisation works?
- If working with metadata: what metadata fields can the software read, what formats does it expect, and does the origin of the record matter?
- How will the model handle data gaps? This is especially relevant if you will be expected to use your own data to train the model (depending on the use case, this may be required).
 - Many (non-generative) algorithms do not like blanks and/or may not handle them well in their training data. Understanding how this will be or ought to be handled is essential.
- Is there a data ownership agreement?
- What are the risks of a data breach?
- What will happen if there is a data breach?
- How would a breach affect your services?

Use cases

- What media and file types are supported?
- If this AI analyses data files, what types of data can it process and what conventions must the data files follow?
- What kinds of interoperability are supported?
- What can it be used for? What can it NOT be used for?
 - Arguably, knowing what it cannot be used for is equally – if not more – important.
- Is there a potential for ‘resource-lock’? E.g. will the software only work with resources or records from specific vendors?
- Is there an agreement with the product vendor on what data has commercial value and how its value will be protected?
 - Does this agreement include protection of privacy, confidentiality and intellectual property (for the seller as well!)?

Development

- How is the model trained?
 - Has it been trained on real data or [synthetic data](#)?
- Will it be re-trained to use in your local setting? If so, who will be doing this?
- How often will the model be updated or retrained?
- What performance metrics were used?
- If you are not training it yourself, what are the [confidence/accuracy levels](#)#?
- What [benchmarking](#) is used?
- Are there benchmarks¹ for your use case?
 - Can you do your own benchmarking?

¹ It seems that within library applications, we do not yet have benchmarks relevant to our specific needs. I expect (and hope) these will be developed as technology develops. Nevertheless, asking vendors about these in advance may push in their development. To learn more you could explore the [Stanford AI index](#) or [this chapter from the Tiny Machine Learning Class book by Harvard \(slightly more technical\)](#).

- Who is the target demographic or 'target user' for this technology and what skills are they assumed to have?

The following questions are more in-depth and technical. You may wish to consult someone in your environment more comfortable with technical terms if you are not.

- What kind of algorithm does the model use?
- Does the algorithm match your use case?
- What is the advertised confidence of the model and does this potentially differ for different applications?
- When using generative AI, can you modify the [creativity](#) of the model?
- Can the software use raw data, or will it require enriched / processed data?
- What was the size of the [training/testing set](#)?
- Can or will additional training take place, based on your local setting, using the low-confidence cases?
- What is the recommended [testing-training](#) cycle?

Support

- What kind of training is available for staff?
 - For technical staff?
 - For non-technical staff?
 - When does training take place (e.g. once upon onboarding or regularly with software releases)?
- What support is available?
 - For technical staff?
 - For non-technical staff?
- What kind of documentation is available?
 - For technical staff?
 - For non-technical staff?

Decommissioning

- What will happen to data not held locally?
- How will decommissioning affect existing data, files, formats and workflows?
 - Will it break existing files and infrastructure that existed before the AI software was added to the system?

Ethics

- What kind of [guardrails](#) are in place for this software?
- Has the privacy of the users been safeguarded?
- What kind of biases may be present in the model?
- Has the training data been assessed for bias?
- If this is an AI that will help inform decisions about people, can users appeal these decisions? This is unlikely to be relevant in a collections setting, but very important to check if it is relevant.
- Will the software notify a user if they attempt to use it for a task outside of its scope?